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Discussion on a safe approach to creating humorous ads for Premium brands: A thematic analysis

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Abstract

The concept of humorous ads has been extensively applied by numerous brands and the results have often been impactful and advantageous for their business. However, when it comes to premium brands, indecisiveness still remains. Many premium brands avoid the use of humor in their ads so as to maintain their elegance. Others, however, have taken a risk and have been experimenting with this unknown substance. The research aims to identify a safe approach that would help premium brands use humor in their ads while keeping their prestige and elegance intact. The study derives four themes which are brand recall, brand perception, purchase intention, and critical elements for creating humorous ads for premium brands. While humor had positive impact on brand recall and brand perception, it was indifferent to the buying behavior of respondents. The study found that appropriate messages, the use of public figures, and relevant ad messages were the key factors that would help premium brands.

Keywords: Advertising; Humor; Premium brands; Recall; Brand perception; Purchase intention

1. Introduction

The word "Advertising" originates from the Latin word "advertere," which means "to turn the attention" (Akrani, 2012). It was once regarded to be a public announcement. However, today's advertising goes beyond making nugatory announcements since it influences potential customers, generates demand, shapes brand preferences, fosters engagement, and boosts sales. Advertising is not directed at a single person, but rather at a group of people. These groups of people are the target audience, who are also potential clients. To define, advertising is a paid method of impersonal communication with a target audience through mass media like television, newspapers, magazines, radio, or the internet (Frolova, 2014).

There are countless businesses today that use humor in their advertisements. Consumers are interested in enjoyable content that helps them break the monotony, even for a brief period of time. Marketers thus employ comedy as a tool to pique consumer interest. Through an engaging, thought-provoking, and memorable message, humor aids in capturing the attention of consumers. According to research, 72% of consumers would pick a brand that uses humor above the competition, and 91% of people prefer humorous brands (Boost10x, 2022). According to World Happiness Report (2022), many people haven't experienced pure happiness in more than two years due to the pandemic, and they're looking for any means necessary to find it and pay a premium when they receive it. David Ogilvy, the father of advertising coined the phrase "The best ideas come as jokes". He suggested that marketers should infuse fun into their content and make their ads as engaging for them to be effective (Lascala, 2022).

Humor in advertising now serves much more purposes than just attracting customers. It is the most widely used tool today that conveys joy and dispels anxiety and worry, even for a brief period of time. For the premium industry,

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however, humor is typically avoided at all costs. Instead, businesses frequently emphasize prestige, aspiration, and heritage—certainly, not characteristics connected to cheap chuckles. This can, however, also give brands an air of stuffiness and even discrimination, raising the bar for consumers to buy in (Gilliand, 2018). So, in this paper, we try to study and identify a safe approach to the usage of humor for premium brands which would ignite affinity towards the brand while keeping intact the brand's heritage and glamour.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Defining Humor in advertising

Since humor is subjective, it is difficult, if not impossible, to define it and provide an answer to the question "why do we laugh?". Humor can sometimes be interpreted differently because different things make different people laugh, and different people may come from different backgrounds. In different contexts, what is perceived as humorous may be cynically viewed. As a result, the lines between humor and its associated ideas (such as wit, amusement, sarcasm, sense of humor, and joking) are sometimes difficult to distinguish between, leading to confusion (Wrench & McCroskey, 2009). Given the term's varied meanings and functions, it makes sense that there isn't a formal definition. Therefore, to lay an informal definition of the term, humor is referred to as a quality that is attached to a particular act, event, object, observation, or statement. In itself, the term "humor" is a very new invention. To state the textbook definition of humor, Romero and Cruthirds (2006) define humor as "amusing communications that promote good emotions and cognitions in the individual, group, or organization." According to the Oxford English Dictionary, it originated in the 17th century as a result of psycho-physiological scientific theory on how different humors can impact a person's temperament.

There are many different interpretations of humor, and there is no universal definition of what humor is. While humor has long found its way into advertising, it is still unclear what humor will best serve to sell the product and what humor may offend the target audience; clearly, not all humorous ads are successful (Barriopedro & Klusek, 2019).

The national differences among individuals undoubtedly have an impact on the perception of humor and their preferences for the style of humor utilized in a given market. Due to cultural effects, the standardization vs adaptation debate cannot be applied to all commercials equally, which therefore has a consequence on the variation of its definition.

2.2. Humor and its appropriate usage in advertising

In the Journal of Advertising, Weinberger (1984) concluded that 55% of executives came to the conclusion that humor is more effective in attracting attention than the absence of it, and 72% said that humor draws customers to new products. Martin Eisend's meta-analysis of humor in advertising shows that humor in advertising greatly increases attention, pleasant effect, and purchase intention. It is essential to use comedy in commercials in a respectable manner. Races, cultures, religions, and disabilities are frequently made fun of to amuse the audience (Eisend, 2009). Such humorous usage may increase stereotypes and discrimination against the brand and deteriorate goodwill. According to Olenski (2018), the wrong joke at the wrong time can create an amateurish image for the brand, and cracking jokes just for the sole purpose of deriving attention can be perceived as exploitative rather than funny. Furthermore, in a survey, by Sprout Social (2017), 88% of customers found it upsetting when an advertisement made a mockery of individuals.

Below are the guidelines set up by Sekulovska (2007), for advertisers on the effective use of humor

Table 1 Guideline by Sekulovska for advertisers for the use of humor

Sl.No	Guideline
1	The humor must serve the purpose of the product. The product, its usage, its features, and its advantages must all be described.
2	Humor should make the advertisement and the advertised goods more appealing. When utilizing hilarious advertising, businesses must exercise extreme caution so as not to harm or disregard the product. The ultimate objective of humor is to increase product sales.
3	Humor must be viewed as a marketing tool to persuade customers to purchase the product.
4	Humor needs to be appropriate for the intended audience.
5	A shared experience is necessary for humor to exist. Demographic, psychographic, religious, and cultural aspects as a result have an impact on it.

6	Businesses must stay away from crude humor. They are not allowed to make fun of the ill, the aged, socially weak, ethnic groups, etc. Humor must respect people's dignity.
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2.3. Premium brands

Everyone aspires to own premium brands since most buyers do so as a status symbol and to project an air of luxury (Neog, 2020). In fact, during the past several hundred years, a large number of premium brands have emerged all over the world. The first and second world wars, or democratization, opened the door for the introduction of new contemporary premium products. Globalization provides a wide range of premium brands. Improvements in business, the national economy, rising investments, and rising spending all have an impact on that (Ashraf, Li, & Mehmood, 2017).

According to Nielsen's (2016) survey, premium brands are defined as those that cost at least 20% more than the average category price and are experiencing above-average growth in numerous fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) categories. But the study found that buyers believe these brands' value goes beyond their price (Discover Data, 2018). Premium brands are those that cost more than the majority of their competitors on the market; as a result, consumers must perceive value in the premium price in order to justify their purchase. Premium brands are distinguished by their high price-to-quality ratio, excellent quality, multiple features, or other competitive advantages or special benefits (Hopper, 2021).

Figure 1 Luxury, fashion and premium positioning triangle (Cherrie & Tyborgnes, 2017)

The terms luxury and premium are frequently used interchangeably, including in marketing literature, however, there are some significant differences between the two. Many businesses position luxury and premium products as distinct entities in their customers' minds by using a triangle of positioning vectors. A luxury product may be perceived as a prestigious entity and may not always give consumers value for their money. A premium product is perceived as an exceptional value as a means of expressing the consumers' lifestyle, however, does not provide buyers with a sense of status or an emotional attachment (Cherrie & Tyborgnes, 2017).

According to Nielsen (2016), the majority (54%) of respondents from throughout the globe said that premium brands are distinguished by their use of quality material or ingredients, while another 46% said that they have superior functionality or performance. Less than one-third (31%) of respondents disagreed, claiming that a premium is not necessarily expensive. Instead, characteristics like the product's superior design (38%), affiliation with a reputable or well-known brand (38%), and provision of a unique feature not offered by any competing product (37%) are more likely to be connected with the term premium brands (Marketing charts, 2017).

2.4. Brand recall

Brand recall measures how effectively a customer can recall a brand in a specific circumstance. Brand recall is the brand that immediately comes to the mind of consumers when they are questioned about a specific product category. It is a significantly stronger link that leads to the actual purchase (Somani, 2021). Moreover, brand recall relates to consumers' aptitude to identify the brand from memory given the product category, the needs fulfilled by the level, and purchase or use according to the situation (Memon, Arif, & Farrukh, 2016).

According to Gelb & Zinkhan (1986), humour has no discernible effect on comprehension or "particularly, the ability to "play back" an information clearly," and the seriousness of the advertisement made no impact either. When

examining the effects of humor in advertising, a 1993 study by the Journal of Marketing concluded that humor is more likely to improve recall, and buying behavior when the humorous statement aligns with ad objectives, and is regarded as suitable for the product category. In such situations, humorous advertising is more likely to capture audience interest, increase recall, overcome sales resistance, and strengthen message salience (Point Park University, 2021).

Further, consumers reported that humorous advertisements are the ones they are most likely to remember and like (Carufel, 2018). Additionally, humorous advertising frequently receives the highest ratings from customers. In Northwestern University's annual Kellogg School Super Bowl Advertising Review, all six companies that received an "A" mark for their Super Bowl advertisements produced amusing commercials that dominated the conversation for more than a week (Carufel, 2018).

2.5. Brand perception

Brand perception alludes to the degree to which clients can review or perceive a brand (Melchor, 2022). Since the 1960s, American businesses have realized that audiences strongly dislike interruptions from marketing and advertising and that these disruptions could be lessened by humor elements, which remove prejudice and anxiety, elevate moods, and unintentionally advance marketing objectives (Spotts & Weinberger, 1997). Beard (2005) suggests that an effective hilarious commercial can not only amuse viewers but also lessen viewers' negative perceptions of the company or product, accomplishing the purpose of advertisements.

Humorous advertisements are more successful than their non-funny counterparts at influencing consumer perceptions and purchasing decisions when prior appraisal of the advertised brand is favorable. The contrary is true when customers have a bad perception already: a hilarious commercial is less effective at altering consumer attitudes and purchasing behavior than its non-comical counterpart (Chattopadhyay & Basu, 1990).

A preconceived notion of luxury brands being unapproachable has been ingrained in the minds of customers for a mammoth amount of time. For premium brands, associating with humorous advertisements can help to dispel these misconceptions. Therefore, the paper is to examine if humor in the ads of luxury products can change how a consumer perceives the brand. The paper deals with products that have been priced 20% more than the average category price.

Research Objectives

The objectives of this research paper:

- To determine the effectiveness of humor in advertising based on brand recall and brand perception for premium brands.
- To identify a safe approach for creating humorous ads for premium brands.

3. Material and methods

In this research, data was gathered by the means of semi-structured interviews to explore the understanding of humor and its usage for premium brands. The interview allowed the researcher to probe more deeply into the interviewees' experiences while also obtaining factual information. The interview guideline was developed with reference to previous studies, consisting of questions dealing with humor, brand recall, brand perception, and premium brands. According to Sandelowski (1995), it is impossible to estimate or perform power analysis in qualitative research to establish the minimal number of necessary sample units. Sandelowski (1995) argued that the main objective is to make sure that the sample size is both manageable for the data and sufficient for "a new and richly textured understanding of experience". In the guidelines for thematic analysis, Braun & Clarke (2013) divide suggestions into categories based on the type of data collection and the project size ('small', 'medium', or 'big'). Accordingly, 6–10 individuals were advised for interviews and 2–4 for focus groups for minor projects.

For this study, a purposive sampling method was used where 15 respondents were selected based on their knowledge of humorous advertising and their satisfactory monthly income level. The incomes of the respondents were taken into account so that the budget constraints were eliminated while answering the question of purchasing premium brands. Many times, the responses are often clouded due to their incapacity to purchase a certain product which can lead to a biased opinion. Respondents had a substantial age gap, some being 25 years apart from each other. This was done so as to consider the opinions of different generations. The interviews were conducted face-to-face and through zoom calls which lasted an average of 20 minutes.

Table 2 Interview Questions with references

Questions	Reference
When you think of humorous ads, what comes to your mind? Do you like humorous ads in general?	(Dinana & Eltazy, 2019)
Will you be able to remember a humorous ad after two days?	(Palikhe, 2019)
Do you think humorous ads are appropriate for premium brands?	(AnalogFolk, 2020)
Would you buy a premium brand after a humorous ad? What factors might you consider before purchasing the premium product?	(Palikhe, 2019)
What do you think would work for premium brands if they had humor in their advertising?	-
Do you feel adding humor in the ads of premium brands would make the brand more customer friendly and induce emotional attachment?	(Aquino, 2021)
Do you think using humor in the ads of premium brands would lessen the brand's status as elegant?	(Loukakis, 2020)

The interviews in this study are interpreted using thematic analysis, one of the qualitative data analysis methods. Thematic analysis approach is used in order to pinpoint the recurring themes, subjects, concepts, and patterns of meaning. The theoretical flexibility of theme analysis, according to Braun and Clarke (2006), makes it an effective research technique that may provide a "rich and detailed, yet complex, description of the data" (Delve, 2020). In their publication, "Using thematic analysis in psychology," Braun and Clarke (2006) describe their thematic analysis methodology which involves a series of six steps (Braun & Clarke, 2006). This paper has used the same research approach. Table II provides the details of the participants.

Table 3 List of respondents with their demographics

ID	Age	Gender	Approx. monthly income (Rs.)
1	31	Female	35,000
2	28	Female	37,500
3	28	Male	32,000
4	30	Female	29,000
5	33	Male	33,000
6	27	Female	35,000
7	29	Female	32,500
8	30	Male	30,000
9	59	Male	33,000
10	55	Male	32,000
11	44	Female	28,000
12	34	Female	30,000
13	27	Female	37,000
14	32	Male	36,000
15	28	Female	29,500

Table 4 Coding template

Topics	Code	Contributions
Brand recall	Memorability, Persuasiveness, secure attention	> "A funny ad definitely lingers in my mind for several days and can be mentioned to friends over a drink or dinner as a conversation starter." > "I would definitely be able to remember a brand through its humorous ads. I still remember the Fevicol humorous ads that were aired 4 years ago."
Humorous ads contribute to emotional attachment to premium brands.	Customer-friendly, brand loyalty, relatable, brand awareness	> "Absolutely. Associating happiness to products makes it customer friendly." > "To some people, it works best, while others may not deem it fine. Basically, humor, if I say, makes a man get more involved with the thing (the ad), more than any other technique."
Purchase of premium brand after a humorous ad	Product quality, Product price	> "A humorous ad is most likely not the leading factor that I consider before buying a premium product. I consider the price." > "I often go for a premium brand for the quality of the product and less likely because of an ad. And if couture shows are too funny for me then maybe but then again it's an artistic impression but is not humorous right...Also, I think humor can be subjective so this is very tricky."
Humorous ads and their effect on premium brand's status	Elegance can be tarnished, No difference,	> "Cheap humor may degrade the brand's status and make them less prestigious." > "If the humor has been used appropriately then it really makes no such difference in the brand's status."
Safe approach for developing humorous ads for premium brands	Appropriate message, Using public figures, Safe humor, Uniqueness	> "Emphasis on uniqueness can definitely work for a premium brand." > "Using public figures because they're the new royals and can garner public enthusiasm." > "Appropriate message is definitely the right choice."

4. Results

Based on the analysis, the themes that emerged were categorized under the broad concepts of (i) brand recall, (ii) brand perception, (iii) purchase intention and (iv) elements to use in humorous ads for premium brands

Figure 2 Conceptual framework on purchase intention

4.1. Theme 1: Brand recall

Increasingly respondents expressed a positive impact of humorous ads on brand recall. The interviewees also demonstrated their likeliness towards humorous ads over other normal ads which were one of the factors supporting their memorability for humorous ads.

Two sub-themes for brand recall were identified which were (i) memorability and (ii) secure attention. Many participants described humorous ads to have a positive effect on memorability. Due to its creativity, many said that it creates a lasting impression on their minds and they can remember it even after a week or more. *For me, if the ad is really funny and interesting then I am able to recall it for a substantial period of time. I still remember humorous ads from my childhood days* (Interview 10). Humor appeals to most people and due to this characteristic, it easily secures the audience's attention and hooks them to stay longer which other normal ads would fail to conduct. *Humorous ads make me want to watch them till the end and see how it relates to products and services. I like humorous ads because it keeps me hooked* (Interviewee 8).

4.2. Theme 2: Brand perception

The respondents indicated that the usage of humor by premium brands would certainly increase their affinity towards the brand. In particular, humorous ads are increasingly being seen as the best marketing technique to make brands more accessible and customer-friendly. If I know the brand is customer-friendly, I would definitely engage more with the brand, and what best than humor for premium brands to make them look more cordial (Interviewee 14). Humorous ads were also recognized by the participants as an aid to increase brand awareness. While the premium product maybe only is of interest to a subset of people, a clever and humorous product can at least raise brand awareness as consumers spread the advertisement to their social networks. The likelihood that the advertisement will reach the targeted subgroup or even expand the market base is higher (Interviewee 10).

While some respondents contradicted the use of humor in premium brands, saying that Cheap humor may degrade the brand's status and make them less prestigious (Interviewee 4) and Humor is not for premium brands. The brand should focus on aspirations and avoid cheap laughs (Interviewee 3), many still viewed humor as a method to make the premium brands more relatable to the customers. Associating happiness with premium products makes them customer-friendly (Interviewee 6). And to 12 out of 15 respondents, adding humor to premium brands certainly made no damage to the brand's status and elegance.

4.3. Theme 3: Purchase intention

While a humorous ad was certainly the most engaging tool to captivate the audience, it was not the leading factor for respondents to make a purchase. *A humorous ad is most likely not the leading factor that I would consider before buying a premium product. I consider the price* (Interviewee 7). Respondents were inclined towards the price and the quality of the product and humorous ads made little to no difference in their purchasing habits.

Few of the respondents indicated that humorous ads can increase their liking of premium brands and for that reason, they might even opt to look for a purchase. But they would certainly scrutinize the quality and price of the product before making the actual purchase. *Buying premium products usually depend on my needs but I would love to buy it after a humorous ad, just to associate the product with the laughter it brought. However, I will check the price and quality too* (Interviewee 11).

4.4. Theme 4: Elements to use in humorous ads for premium brands

The most recurring element during this segment was "appropriate message" followed by "use of public figures" as the response to "What elements would work best for humorous ads of premium brands?". Using appropriate message that is the message that is relevant and concise with no foul intention is very important to maintain the dignity of the premium brands. Sometimes it so happens that the marketers forget to focus on the heritage of the brand while developing humorous ads which can lead to accusations and questions about brand credibility. *It is important that premium brands focus on the message. If the message is interpreted wrongly then the entire brand will be at stake* (Interviewee 9). The use of public figures can be another element to use in humorous ads. *Using public figures because they're the new royals and can garner public enthusiasm. Plus, they help maintain brand credibility* (Interviewee 11).

While few of the respondents still felt that using humor for premium brands was unnecessary and just a bad marketing strategy to degrade the brand, they suggested that if the humor was used with careful strategy and unique characteristics, it might work. *I don't feel humorous ads are the right way to go for premium brands. However, if the message is appropriate and does not discriminate against anyone, then it may work for premium brands* (Interviewee 9).

Many premium brands are striving for humorous content in their ads so as to make their brands more relatable and accessible to customers. For some brands, this strategy has effectively worked to garner customer retention. However, to some brands, this marketing tool has backfired and customers now have an opinionated outlook toward those brands. For this reason, it is necessary to use humor with great care and instigate the right message in the minds of the consumers.

Elements such as safe humor, relatable message, simple presentation, and creative humor were among the other suggestions that respondents preferred in the humorous ads of premium brands. *Another element that might work for premium brands is to ensure that their message will resonate with their target audience* (Interviewee 2). *I prefer unique and creative ads over anything and I assume that it will work for premium brands too* (Interviewee 15).

In addition, messages related to the product were mentioned for the humor to work for premium brands. *Humor should work if the message is relevant to the product and does not stray away from the ad's objective* (Interviewee 7).

5. Discussions

The respective research findings shed light on the effectiveness of humor on brand recall and brand perception for premium brands by detailing and analyzing the thoughts of the respondents on these topics and also identifying a safe approach that would help the premium brands to present themselves as customer-friendly and accessible while maintaining their prestige and status.

Based on the thematic analysis, four broad themes emerged (brand recall, brand perception, purchase intention, and elements to use in the humorous ads of premium brands). From the interviews, it was indicated that humor had a positive impact on brand recall and respondents would definitely remember a humorous ad for a long period of time. Humor also had an impact on changing the perceptions of the respondents toward premium brands. Many respondents mentioned that through humorous ads, premium brands are seen as more customer-friendly and approachable. These findings are supported by the research conducted by Thomas and James (2013).

In this research, there were mostly three prevalent elements that respondents suggested marketers should use while developing humorous ads for premium brands

Figure 3 Key elements to use for humorous ads for premium brands

5.1. Element 1: Appropriate message

An advertising message is an idea that an advertiser wishes to convey to their target audience. Its objective is to persuade customers to carry out a specific activity, such as making a purchase or booking a reservation. The appropriate advertising message aids in conveying the right idea to the public, enabling brands to establish enduring and trustful relationships with their target market (Greene, 2022).

Some of the attributes of an appropriate advertising message according to Balanos & Vidal (2022) are messages that are persuasive, original, and have no foul language or no discriminatory essence. Some other attributes that were suggested by the respondents of this research paper that would build an appropriate advertising message were relevancy, compel, and concise.

5.2. Element 2: Public figure

People are inclined to trust a recommendation or endorsement from a known public figure. Public figures are people who have attained all-encompassing renown or infamy. They hold a lot of public interest and have the power to readily change people's habits (Meloy, 2014). Brands use public figures because they are trusted by their audience which helps build their brand credibility. By using a company's goods, they demonstrate to their followers that it is a quality item and establish credibility for the company. When a celebrity's name is associated with a product, consumers are more assured of its quality. Therefore, the use of public figures can put premium brands on the safe side and make the humorous ads fun as well as have the essence of credibility and elegance to them.

5.3. Element 3: Message related to product

The studies conducted by Scott et al. (1995) found that the use of humor that is closely tied to and interwoven with the messages that the advertisement raises, as well as having already vetted the product, is the most effective way to reach customers. To have a favorable impact, the message must be purposefully, thematically, or structurally tied to the product. When humor is powerful and relevant to the message, advertising is more memorable, and this interaction is mediated by attention and mood (Barriopedro, 2019).

Additionally, humor should not dominate the announcement in order to attract and hold viewers' attention, but rather the message that is intended to be conveyed. If this occurs, the brand or product that is being announced, which is the main purpose of the advertisement, may be forgotten in favor of the announcement's humor (Spotts & Weinberger, 1997). Thus, to see the possible consequences among consumers, in addition to using public figures and humor, the relevant message needs to be an essential factor.

Practical implications

In an effort to make their brands more affable and accessible, premium brands are suggested to use humor in their ads. The findings of this study indicate that using humor might serve as an advantageous strategy for premium brands since it has a positive impact on brand recall and brand perception. Respondents mentioned that they were able to remember brands that were associated with humorous ads. This knowledge could be used by marketing and media executives of premium brands to integrate humor in their advertisements and promote their products and services more effectively.

Due to the distant nature of the premium brand industry, consumers often regard premium brands as unapproachable. In addition, a lot of consumers believe that these brands are primarily intended for the elites and upper-class society. Thus, using humor can certainly eliminate such stereotypes

According to the findings of this study, the effectiveness of humorous commercials for premium brands depends on three factors; appropriate message, relevant message, and well-known public figures. The marketing and ad development departments of premium brands can utilize these factors to protect their reputation while attracting new customers to their business. The aim is to use these components in a way that draws in more customer footfall and changes the brand's image to one that is more welcoming to them. These factors would not only give the brand a competitive edge in the market, but it would also help premium brands to enter previously inaccessible markets. The results of this study would help improve the ways the premium brand has been using humor in their ads.

Limitations of the study

It is quite common to be confronted by problems and difficulties when dealing with a topic that cannot be quantified. Study on Humor remains one such topic. Listed are some limitations of this research study that focuses on using humorous ads on premium brands:

Difficulty in measuring humor: Humor is a subjective matter; therefore, what one person finds humorous may not be the same for another. As people's tastes in humor differ widely, it can be difficult for studies to gauge the impact of humor in advertising.

- Cultural differences: Cultural differences have a big impact on humor, so what is funny in one culture could not be in another. This can limit the generalizability of the results of a study focusing on humorous ads for premium brands.
- Brand image: Humorous ads can be risky for premium brands, as they may damage the brand image if the humor is perceived as inappropriate or offensive. Researchers must take into account the potential impact of humor on the brand image and reputation. Premium brands may also be hesitant to invest in humorous advertisements if they are concerned about the potential negative impact on their brand image.
- Budget constraints: While the income factor of the respondents were taken into account, the respondents were still fixating on the price of the product. Their purchase intention for a premium brand that displayed a humorous ad mostly depended on the price range of the product. This made it difficult to realize the true effectiveness of humorous ads on premium brands.

Recommendations for future research

Due to the study's constrained resources, the extent of the research is inherently limited. This opens up possibilities for further investigation into how specific type of humor, such as situational, or black humor, or other classification of humor can have an impact on the three themes as discussed in this study. The influence of various emotional appeals in advertisements can also be investigated using the research techniques utilized in this study. By dedicating more resources, such as people and facilities to assist the interviews, more insights can be gained through in-depth interviews. Focus groups and recording equipment could be used in a related study to better observe the respondents.

6. Conclusion

The present study determined the effectiveness of humor based on brand recall and brand perception for premium brands, in addition to the finding of a safe approach that would enable premium brands to use humor while maintaining their status and elegance. The results demonstrated evidence of humor having a possible impact on consumers' memorability and that a humorous ad was something the respondents preferred over a normal non-humorous ad. Humor also evidently worked as a leading factor to change the perception of people towards premium brands, that is, a premium brand might come out as more customer friendly and approachable if humor is added to their ads. Other than these two themes, purchase intention and key elements for developing humorous ads for premium brands were identified, wherein it was found that humor had no such impact on the buying habits of the consumers. The consumers were more focused on price and quality of the product rather than a humorous ad when it comes to making an actual purchase. Through the analysis, three key elements were identified that would best work for premium brands while developing humorous ads, which were (i) appropriate message, (ii) public figures, and (iii) message related to the product.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

Author Neha Powrel and Swapna H R have no problem in publishing in your esteemed journal. We declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the research discussed in this paper. We have no financial or personal relationships with any individuals or organizations that could potentially bias my research findings.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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